

THERMAL STRESS AND HEAT TRANSFER ANALYSIS OF A THERMIONIC WASTE HEAT RECOVERY SYSTEM DESIGNED FOR A HYBRID ELECTRIC VEHICLE

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Abstract

This paper presents the simulation-based analysis and performance evaluation of a Thermionic Energy Converter (TEC) system designed for automotive exhaust heat recovery. The proposed system, modeled using Multiphysics software, investigates the effects of various material properties and temperature gradients on thermal stress, thermal strain, and heat transfer efficiency. High-performance materials such as Tungsten and Molybdenum demonstrated superior thermionic conversion capabilities, achieving heat transfer rates of 1038.73 W and 985.43 W, respectively. Additionally, these materials exhibited low thermal stress and strain under operating conditions, validating their suitability for high-temperature TEC components. Coated Graphene showed the highest heat flux (2107.09 W), indicating its potential for enhancing conversion efficiency, although practical coating challenges remain. The simulation outcomes underscore the effectiveness of numerical modeling for material selection and design optimization in TEC systems. Future work involves experimental validation under dynamic thermal loads and further exploration of advanced coating methodologies to improve TEC performance.

Keywords: Thermionic Energy Converter (TEC), Waste Heat Recovery, Thermal Stress, Thermal Strain, Heat Transfer, Tungsten, Molybdenum, Coated Graphene, Simulation, Automotive Exhaust System, Multiphysics Modeling, Work Function, Conversion Efficiency

INTRODUCTION

The rapid increase in fossil-fuelled vehicles has caused significant environmental harm, accelerating climate change, air pollution, and resource depletion. In response, Hybrid Electric Vehicles (HEVs) have emerged as a sustainable alternative, combining internal combustion engines with electric motors to reduce fuel consumption and emissions [1]. HEVs also utilize regenerative braking to recover kinetic energy, improving fuel efficiency and extending driving range by up to 25% [2,3]. Despite these benefits, a large portion of energy is still lost as waste heat, especially through the exhaust, where temperatures can reach 950°C. This presents an opportunity for waste heat recovery using direct heat-to-electricity methods like Thermoelectric (TEG) and Thermionic Energy Conversion (TIC). While TEGs are widely studied, TIC is more suitable for high-temperature environments. TIC works on the principle of thermionic emission, where heat energy frees electrons from a heated emitter surface. These electrons cross a vacuum gap to a cooler collector, generating electrical power [4–5]. Materials with low work functions are ideal for emission within automotive exhaust temperature ranges (600–950°C) [6,7]. A basic TEC unit includes an emitter and a collector separated by a vacuum. Historically used in space due to extreme heat requirements (>2000°C),

recent material advancements now allow TECs to operate efficiently at lower temperatures, making them viable for HEVs [8,9]. In HEVs, the exhaust manifold is an ideal location for TEC integration due to its high thermal potential. TEC performance depends on factors like gas flow, viscosity, and temperature gradients [10]. However, fluctuating exhaust conditions, vibrations, and mechanical stress can challenge TEC durability. Therefore, analysing thermal stress is vital to ensure long-term reliability in automotive environments [11].

LITERATURE REVIEW

Thermionic Energy Conversion (TEC) is a heat-to-electricity technology historically used in space applications due to extreme temperature gradients. Recent advancements in materials and nanotechnology have renewed interest in adapting TECs for terrestrial applications, especially in the automotive sector for waste heat recovery and improving hybrid vehicle (HEV) efficiency.

Several studies highlight hybrid systems combining fuel cells, thermoelectric generators (TEGs), and TECs. Yan et al. [12] demonstrated a 2.73-fold increase in power using a hybrid fuel cell–TEG system, emphasizing design and operational optimization. Bhakta and Kundu [13] reviewed TEG advancements in automobiles, covering novel materials and heat exchanger designs. Complementing TEGs, **heat pipes** offer compact, high-efficiency thermal management. Jose et al. [29] reviewed their role in waste heat recovery, noting the benefits of nanofluids and metal foams. Sadik and Mehdi [14] addressed thermoelectric material challenges, especially thermal stress. Zaferani et al. [27] advocated combining solid-state energy converters like TEGs and TECs to reduce emissions. Wang et al. [28] studied supercritical CO₂ systems to manage thermal stress, findings relevant for TECs under fluctuating conditions. Vizitiu et al. [24] showed 76.7% heat recovery using heat pipes—adaptable for hybrid vehicles. Kodihal and Sagar [18,20] explored small-scale TECs for HEVs, addressing space charge effects and using nanomaterials like graphene to improve emission efficiency. De and Olawole [21] developed a 3D model for predicting thermionic current with graphene and CNTs, aiding design precision. Shittu et al. [25] addressed contact resistance in segmented thermoelectric systems, a challenge TECs also face. Vaferi and Nekahi [26] showed TiB₂ performs well under thermal stress, making it suitable for TEC emitters.

Jouhara et al. [22] identified TECs as promising for both industrial and automotive use. Khalid et al. [8] revisited vacuum-based TECs and their challenges, including space charge effects and material degradation. Structural durability studies by Jeon et al. [19] and thermal modeling by Spitsov et al. [13] and Xin & Qianfan [15] provide insights for robust TEC integration. Thermal protection strategies, such as those discussed by Sadowski et al. [17] for aero-engine blades, are applicable to TEC durability. Bibin et al. [18] proposed combining TEGs with turbocharging—an idea that TECs could emulate. Ozceyhan et al. [23] emphasized optimizing pipe flow and surface geometry, useful for TEC emitter/collector design. Kanazaki and Morikawa [16] and Kim et al. [15] explored system-level optimizations that can reduce thermal stress during transient engine operations. **In summary**, while TEGs have broader use, the literature highlights TEC's growing potential in HEVs, particularly with nanostructured materials, compact high-temp designs, and hybrid energy recovery systems. TECs offer a promising path for enhancing energy efficiency and reducing emissions in future vehicle technologies.

RESEARCH GAPS

Despite rising interest in Thermionic Energy Conversion (TEC) for HEVs, key challenges remain. Studies rarely address real-world thermal fluctuations, and long-term high-temperature durability is underexplored. Most designs overlook exhaust system constraints, and few use coupled thermal-mechanical models. Retrofitting lacks clear guidelines, and real-world prototype validation is still limited.

OBJECTIVES

The objectives of this study are to perform a comparative analysis of conventional automotive exhaust materials with those used in Thermionic Energy Conversion (TEC) systems and to examine the effects of thermal stress and strain on TEC materials. A numerical model will be developed to analyze these thermal effects, followed by the design and simulation of a TEC system under such conditions. Finally, the study aims to assess the feasibility of implementing TEC materials within the exhaust system of Hybrid Electric Vehicles (HEVs).

METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a combined mathematical and simulation-based approach to assess the feasibility and performance of integrating Thermionic Energy Converters (TECs) into Hybrid Electric Vehicle (HEV) exhaust systems. The methodology involves analytical modeling of heat transfer and thermal stress, supported by simulation to evaluate real-world performance and design stability. Two platforms were used: LabVIEW for developing mathematical models of heat transfer and electron emission, and COMSOL Multiphysics for simulating thermal stress, heat flow, and the dynamic behavior of the TEC-integrated exhaust system.

Design Considerations

This study focuses on designing a Thermionic Energy Converter (TEC) module suitable for retrofitting into the high-temperature regions of Hybrid Electric Vehicle (HEV) exhaust systems. Due to the extreme thermal and pressure conditions near the exhaust manifold and catalytic converter, careful attention was given to material selection and structural integrity [30]. The area just after the catalytic converter was chosen for TEC integration, as it offers elevated gas temperatures ideal for efficient thermionic emission and energy harvesting [31]. A cylindrical TEC architecture was proposed, offering thermal efficiency, structural symmetry, and aerodynamic compatibility with minimal disruption to exhaust flow. The design ensures precise inter-electrode gap based on operating temperature and material properties, incorporates high-temperature electrical insulation using glass or ceramic to prevent short circuits, and provides dynamic load resilience to withstand engine vibrations and thermal stress. This form factor ensures smooth gas flow, reduces back pressure, and allows seamless integration into existing vehicle exhaust systems while enhancing energy recovery and maintaining mechanical stability.

Figure 1: Prototype Design of Cylindrical TEC

Table 1: Bill of Materials for Cylindrical TEC

Part No.	Quantity	Part Name
1	1	Top Fixture
2	2	Glass Insulator
3	1	Top Guide
4	1	Emitter
5	1	Collector
6	1	Bottom Guide
7	1	Bottom Fixture

Component Breakdown

The proposed cylindrical TEC system comprises several key components, each playing a vital role in ensuring mechanical stability, thermal performance, and electrical insulation. As illustrated in Figure 1, the Top Fixture (Part 1) acts as the structural anchor, maintaining rigidity and proper alignment of internal elements. Glass Insulators (Part 2)—two units positioned between the emitter and collector—provide high-temperature electrical insulation to ensure safe and uninterrupted electron flow. The Top Guide (Part 3) aligns the emitter and collector along the cylindrical axis, preserving the critical inter-electrode gap required for efficient thermionic emission. At the core of the system is the Emitter (Part 4), constructed from low work function materials to absorb exhaust heat and emit electrons effectively. Opposite it, the Collector (Part 5) captures the emitted electrons and connects to the external electrical circuit, functioning at a relatively cooler temperature to enhance energy harvesting. The Bottom Guide (Part 6) provides alignment and structural support at the base, while the Bottom Fixture (Part 7) serves as the foundation, securing the entire TEC assembly within the exhaust system and ensuring overall stability during operation.

Figure 2: Retrofit Design for Exhaust system

Figure 2 shows the TEC unit retrofitted after the catalytic converter in the HEV exhaust system. The cylindrical design ensures high thermal gradients, stable inter-electrode gap, smooth exhaust flow,

and minimal back pressure, enabling efficient energy harvesting without affecting engine performance.

MATERIAL SELECTION AND THERMAL DESIGN

Thermal and mechanical stability are crucial when integrating Thermionic Energy Converter (TEC) units into automotive exhaust systems. Materials must endure high temperatures, corrosive gases, and vibrations while enabling efficient electron emission. In HEVs, exhaust components like manifolds use cast iron, stainless steel, or Inconel to handle temperatures up to 950°C. Catalytic converters use ceramic or metallic honeycombs with precious metals, while other parts like bellows, mufflers, pipes, and tailpipes rely on stainless or aluminized steel for durability and corrosion resistance. For TEC components, emitters require materials with low work function and high thermal stability, such as tungsten, molybdenum, or coated graphene. Collectors use nickel alloys, stainless steel, or ceramics for effective electron capture. Insulators like alumina, boron nitride, and glass ensure electrical isolation under heat. The optimal placement for TECs is before the catalytic converter, where high temperatures (600–950°C) enhance emission efficiency. Materials were selected based on their thermal conductivity, mechanical strength, corrosion resistance, and emission properties, as outlined in Table 2.

Table 2: Materials Considered for Analysis

Sr. No.	Material	Description
1	SS400	Composition of silicon, carbon, phosphorus and Sulphur.
2	SUH409L	Composition highly of chromium, titanium, carbon and nitrogen (lower), it's a stable version of grade 409L
3	SUS439L	Useful in applications were complex shapes such as tubular manifolds and exhaust system components are required.
4	SA1D	Aluminum silicon alloy is coated on both sides to form aluminized steel.
5	Tungsten	Tungsten has highest melting temperatures over 1650 ⁰ C. Tensile strength is 1725 MPa and Mohs hardness is 7.5.
6	Molybdenum	A Mohs hardness of molybdenum is 5.5 and a standard atomic weight of 95.95 g/mol. It has a melting point of 2,623 °C.
7	Coated Graphene	It is a single layer of atoms in a two-dimensional hexagonal lattice. In this form atom form a vortex.[26]

Comparative Properties of Selected Materials

A comprehensive analysis of thermal, mechanical, and thermionic emission-related properties is presented in Table 2. These properties inform material suitability for TEC efficiency and structural performance in exhaust systems.

Sr. No.	Material	Melting Point	Thermal Conductivity	Young's Modulus	Work Function	Poisson's Ratio	Density	Coefficient of thermal expansion
.								

		(°C)	ivity (W/mK)	Modul us (GPa)	(eV)		(Kg/m ³)	Expansion (x 10 ⁻⁶)
1	SS400	1430	16	210	4.4	0.26	7860	17.8
2	SUH409L	1510	25	200	4.4	0.3	7750	11.7
3	SUS439L	1505	14	193	4.4	0.29	7700	13
4	SA1D	677	15	200	4.4	0.24	7870	13
5	Tungsten	3410	167.36	700	4.5	0.284	19300	4.3
6	Molybdenum	2623	138	343	4.32	0.29	10220	4.8
7	Coated Graphene	3000	2000	1010	1.1	0.38	2670	1.67

Materials used in TECs must meet several key criteria for optimal performance. A high melting point (e.g., tungsten, molybdenum) ensures stability at exhaust temperatures of 600–950°C. Excellent thermal conductivity, such as that of graphene (2000 W/mK), enhances heat transfer, while a low work function (e.g., graphene: 1.1 eV) improves electron emission. High Young’s modulus values maintain structural integrity under stress, and a high Poisson’s ratio provides flexibility and vibration resistance. Additionally, low density and thermal expansion help reduce stress and extend the system’s operational lifespan.

MATERIAL SELECTION AND THERMAL DESIGN

Analytical Approach and Validation Basis Heat Transfer Analysis

In automotive TEC systems, heat is transferred from exhaust gases to the cathode via internal forced convection. Analyzing this heat transfer is key to optimizing thermionic emission and overall energy conversion. Determines whether the gas flow is laminar or turbulent, directly affecting the heat transfer rate to the emitter surface. It is calculated using standard fluid dynamics equations.

$$R_e = \frac{4m_g}{\pi D \mu} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where:

- m_g = mass flow rate of exhaust gas (Kg/sec)
- μ = viscosity of the gas (Kg/m.sec)
- D = inner diameter of the pipe (m)

The Reynolds number provides insight into the flow pattern of the fluid, which directly affects the heat transfer process. Calculations using the mass flow rate of exhaust gases in a typical automotive exhaust system have shown that the flow is turbulent. In the case of a fully developed turbulent flow (both hydrodynamically and thermally), the Dittus-Boelter equation is employed to calculate the Nusselt number (Nu), which characterizes the convective heat transfer. The equation is expressed as:

$$N_{ud} = 0.023R_{ed}^{0.8}P_r^n \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where:

- N_{ud} = Nusselt number
- R_{ed} = Reynolds number
- P_r = Prandtl number
- $n=0.4$ for heating, $n=0.3$ for cooling

The Dittus-Boelter equation is a commonly used correlation for calculating heat transfer in turbulent fluid flow through pipes. **Coefficient of Heat Transfer (h)** Once the Nusselt number is determined, the **coefficient of heat transfer (h)** can be calculated using the following equation:

$$h = \frac{N_{ud} \times K}{D} \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Where:

- K = thermal conductivity of the exhaust gas (W/m.K)
- D = inner diameter of the pipe (m)

This equation quantifies how efficiently heat transfers from exhaust gases to the pipe’s inner surface, crucial for TEC performance. The heat transfer coefficient indicates how effectively heat reaches the emitter to drive thermionic emission.

Thermal Stress and Strain Analysis

In an exhaust system, the pipe experiences frequent temperature fluctuations—from ambient levels up to 800°C—which generate thermal stresses in the material. Over time, these stresses can cause fatigue, cracking, or failure, impacting the durability of both the exhaust and the integrated TEC system. Thus, analyzing thermal stress and strain is crucial for enhancing TEC reliability and lifespan.

Thermal Stress Calculation:

The thermal stress developed in a material subjected to temperature changes is calculated using the following equation:

$$\sigma = E\alpha(T_f - T_o) \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

- σ = thermal stress (MPa)
- E = Young’s modulus (GPa)
- α = coefficient of thermal expansion ($^{\circ}C^{-1}$)
- T_f = final (maximum) temperature (K)
- T_o = initial (reference) temperature (K)

Alternatively, the thermal stress can be expressed in terms of temperature change ΔT

$$\sigma = E\alpha\Delta T \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

This equation calculates the thermal stress as a function of the temperature difference, material’s Young’s modulus, and its coefficient of thermal expansion. Higher values of ΔT or materials with higher α values will result in larger thermal stresses.

a) **Thermal Strain Calculation:**

b) Thermal strain, which is the deformation caused by thermal stress, is represented by the equation:

$$\epsilon = A\sigma^n f_2(T) \quad (6)$$

ϵ = thermal strain (unitless)

A = stress normalization factor ($3.0 \times 10^{-6}/h$)

n = strain exponent

$f_2(T)$ = temperature-dependent function

The function $f_2(T)$ accounts for the effect of temperature on strain and is given by:

$$f_2(T) = e^{\frac{-12500}{T}} \quad (7)$$

T = maximum temperature in Kelvin (K)

This equation helps predict the strain on the pipe material due to thermal expansion under extreme temperature conditions.

Here, A is stress normalization factor i.e. $3.0 \times 10^{-6}/h$, T is maximum temperature in K, σ in MPa.

Significance of Thermal Stress Analysis:

Thermal stress and strain analysis is vital for ensuring the reliability of the TEC system, as repeated heating and cooling can cause cracks or material failure. Understanding these effects aids in material selection and design optimization, enhancing durability and performance. This analysis ensures the TEC can withstand mechanical and thermal loads, supporting its viability for waste heat recovery in HEVs [27].

Analytical Results:

Thermal stress of Tungsten-

$$E = 700 \text{ GPa}, \alpha = 4.3, T_f = 800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}, T_0 = 30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$$

$$\sigma = (700 \times 10^3)(4.3 \times 10^{-9})(800 - 30)$$

$$\sigma = 2.31 \text{ GPa}$$

Thermal Strain of Tungsten-

$$A = 3 \times 10^{-6}/h, \sigma = 2.31 \text{ GPa}, n = 5.5, f_2(T) = e^{\frac{-12500}{T}}, T = 1073 \text{ }^\circ\text{K}$$

$$\epsilon = \left(\frac{3 \times 10^{-6}}{4.16 \times 10^{-6}} \right) (2.31)^{5.5} \left(e^{\frac{-12500}{1073}} \right)$$

$$\epsilon = 0.00083$$

Thermal stress of Molybdenum-

$$E = 343 \text{ GPa}, \alpha = 4.8, T_f = 800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}, T_0 = 30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$$

$$\sigma = (343 \times 10^3)(4.8 \times 10^{-6})(800 - 30)$$

$$\sigma = 1.27 \text{ GPa}$$

Thermal Strain of Molybdenum-

$$A = 3 \times 10^{-6}/h, \sigma = 1.27 \text{ GPa}, n = 5.5, f_2(T) = e^{\frac{-12500}{T}}, T = 1073 \text{ }^\circ\text{K}$$

$$\epsilon = \left(\frac{3 \times 10^{-6}}{4.16 \times 10^{-6}} \right) (1.27)^{5.5} \left(e^{\frac{-12500}{1073}} \right)$$

$$\epsilon = 0.000027$$

c) Rate of Heat Transfer for Tungsten-

II. CALCULATION FOR MASS FLOW RATE = 0.01 KG/S

1. Calculate Area (A): $A = \pi \times D \times L = 3.1416 \times 0.051 \times 0.068 = 0.010895 \text{ m}^2$	2. Calculate Reynolds Number (Re): $Re = (4 \times 0.01) / (3.1416 \times 0.051 \times 3.5e-05) = 7132.99$
3. Calculate Nusselt Number (Nu): $Nu = 0.023 \times 7132.99^{0.8} \times 0.70^{0.4} = 24.12$	4. Required Thermal Conductivity (K): $K = 0.1323 \text{ W/mK}$
5. Calculate Coefficient of Heat Transfer (h): $h = (24.12 \times 0.1323) / 0.051 = 62.58 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$	6. Calculate Rate of Heat Transfer (Q): $Q = 62.58 \times 0.010895 \times 770 = 525.00 \text{ W}$

Similarly,

III. CALCULATION FOR MASS FLOW RATE = 0.02 KG/S Rate of Heat Transfer (Q): $Q = 88.45 \times 0.010895 \times 770 = 742.00 \text{ W}$	IV. CALCULATION FOR MASS FLOW RATE = 0.03 KG/S Rate of Heat Transfer (Q): $Q = 102.04 \times 0.010895 \times 770 = 856.00 \text{ W}$
V. CALCULATION FOR MASS FLOW RATE = 0.04 KG/S Rate of Heat Transfer (Q): $Q = 122.30 \times 0.010895 \times 770 = 1026.00 \text{ W}$	VI. CALCULATION FOR MASS FLOW RATE = 0.05 KG/S Rate of Heat Transfer (Q): $Q = 134.96 \times 0.010895 \times 770 = 1132.22 \text{ W}$

a)

b) Rate of Heat Transfer for Molybdenum-

VII. CALCULATION FOR MASS FLOW RATE = 0.01 KG/S

1. Calculate Area (A): $A = \pi \times D \times L = 3.1416 \times 0.051 \times 0.068 = 0.010895 \text{ m}^2$	2. Calculate Reynolds Number (Re): $Re = (4 \times 0.01) / (3.1416 \times 0.051 \times 3.5e-05) = 7132.99$
3. Calculate Nusselt Number (Nu): $Nu = 0.023 \times 7132.99^{0.8} \times 0.70^{0.4} = 24.12$	4. Required Thermal Conductivity (K): $K = 0.1209 \text{ W/mK}$
5. Calculate Coefficient of Heat Transfer (h): $h = (24.12 \times 0.1209) / 0.051 = 57.20 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$	6. Calculate Rate of Heat Transfer (Q): $Q = 57.20 \times 0.010895 \times 770 = 479.84 \text{ W}$

Similarly,

VIII. CALCULATION FOR MASS FLOW RATE = 0.02 KG/S Rate of Heat Transfer (Q): $Q = 69.87 \times 0.010895 \times 770 = 586.18 \text{ W}$	IX. CALCULATION FOR MASS FLOW RATE = 0.03 KG/S Rate of Heat Transfer (Q): $Q = 77.25 \times 0.010895 \times 770 = 648.04 \text{ W}$
X. CALCULATION FOR MASS FLOW RATE = 0.04 KG/S Rate of Heat Transfer (Q): $Q = 95.34 \times 0.010895 \times 770 = 799.79 \text{ W}$	XI. CALCULATION FOR MASS FLOW RATE = 0.05 KG/S Rate of Heat Transfer (Q): $Q = 111.79 \times 0.010895 \times 770 = 937.85 \text{ W}$

Design Simulation

Process for Thermally Induced Stress

Finite Element Analysis (FEA), based on NAFEMS standards, was used to study thermal stress in the TEC emitter under high-temperature conditions, focusing on creep and stress buildup. A simplified 2D axisymmetric model of the cylindrical system was used to reduce computation time while still capturing key thermal and stress patterns. The model had an outer diameter of 54 mm and an inner diameter of 51 mm. It was subjected to an internal pressure of 500 kPa (applied over 0.1 seconds) and a temperature field to simulate real exhaust conditions.

$$T=333(1+100/r) \dots\dots\dots (8)$$

where r = radial distance (m)

Thermal and Mechanical Effects

- Inner surface expands more than outer surface ⇒ Thermal stress
- Combined thermal + mechanical loads ⇒ Hoop + axial stresses
- Long-term exposure leads to creep

Heat Transfer and Thermal Stress Simulation

The heat transfer simulation employed an internal forced convection model to analyze gas-to-metal heat transfer, using boundary conditions based on typical engine exhaust temperatures ranging from 600°C to 950°C. Thermal stress simulation accounted for material expansion and contraction, incorporating properties such as Young’s modulus, Poisson’s ratio, and thermal expansion coefficient. Additionally, creep and strain simulations were conducted to model time-dependent deformation using temperature-strain relationships, while also considering material fatigue under cyclic thermal loading to assess long-term reliability.

Results

The simulation showed that stress peaks occur near the inner pipe surface, which is closest to the exhaust gas. The results were validated using NAFEMS benchmarks, ensuring accuracy. The analysis also identified failure-prone zones, highlighting areas where material upgrades or design modifications may be needed to enhance durability and performance.

SIMULATION RESULTS

The models developed using Multiphysics software were simulated by varying material properties and temperature inputs to analyse the thermal stress, thermal strain, and heat transfer rate in the

Thermionic Energy Converter (TEC) system. The results and insights obtained from these simulations are discussed below.

Figure 3: Heat Transfer Analysis Results (Place after this paragraph)

Figure 3 illustrates the correlation between heat transfer rate and exhaust gas mass flow rate across different materials. Coated graphene exhibits the highest heat flux at 2107.09 W, attributed to its superior thermal conductivity, making it highly effective for TEC applications. Tungsten and molybdenum also perform well, with heat transfer rates of 1038.73 W and 985.43 W, respectively, positioning them as strong candidates for thermionic systems. In contrast, steel grades such as SS400, SUH409L, and SUS439L show lower heat transfer rates due to their reduced thermal conductivity, with SA1D having the lowest performance at 322.46 W.

Figure 4. Effect of temperature difference and work function on thermionic conversion efficiency. Figure 4 illustrates how thermionic conversion efficiency is influenced by temperature difference and material work function. Efficiency improves with higher hot electrode temperatures and lower work function values. For instance, at 800°C (hot) and 30°C (cold), efficiency exceeds 15%, while a low work function of 0.75 eV can push efficiency to 20% at just 127°C. This highlights the importance of maximizing temperature gradients and using low work function materials to enhance TEC performance for practical applications.

Figure 5: Thermal Stress Analysis

Thermal stress simulations revealed significant differences in material performance under high thermal loads. SS400 steel exhibited the highest stress at 2.7489 GPa, while tungsten and molybdenum showed lower stress levels of 2.3177 GPa and 1.26773 GPa, respectively. Molybdenum, with the lowest stress, demonstrated superior thermal stability. These results suggest that both tungsten and molybdenum are well-suited for use in TEC systems for automotive exhaust heat recovery.

Figure 6: Thermal Strain Analysis

This figure shows thermal deformation of various materials. SS400 exhibits the highest strain, while tungsten (0.00083) and molybdenum (0.000029) show minimal deformation. Although steel is strong, it deforms more under heat. Thus, tungsten and molybdenum are better suited for TEC components due to their high thermal stability.

Key Insights from the Results

Coated graphene offers the highest heat transfer, but due to challenges at high temperatures, tungsten and molybdenum are more practical choices for TEC applications. Both materials support efficient heat flux and are suitable for automotive waste heat recovery. In terms of thermal stress, tungsten and molybdenum outperform steel by offering better thermal conductivity and lower strain, with molybdenum showing excellent resistance to deformation under high thermal loads. Additionally, thermionic conversion efficiency improves with higher temperature gradients and the use of low work

function materials like tungsten and molybdenum, making them ideal for enhancing TEC performance.

CONCLUSION

Blended learning is a combination of online and offline learning system and they both complement each other. It integrates both real-time as well as self-paced learning experience, allowing students to access study material virtually, getting engaged with educators, and completing their assignments online. One of the single most challenge faced in blended learning is this concept is not yet fully understood by both educators and students. Blended learning extends face-to-face instructions to virtual system. Blended learning, combines traditional classroom instructions with online learning provides inventive approaches as well as strategies addressing challenges faced by educational institutes while leveraging new opportunities of teaching and learning. In order to fully understand the advantages of blended learning and to deal with its limitations, educational system must take important steps for integration of this digital technology in their education learning system. It also includes examining the required digital tools.

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